

The Impact of Government Investments on India's Stock Markets: Insights from the Indian Railway Sector

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ABSTRACT

This paper delves into the significant effect government investments have on the trends within the stock markets present in India, especially those about the railway sector. In a great way, the government's investments, especially in the micro, small, and medium enterprises, the tourism industry, and the agriculture sector, greatly assist and support improvement in economic growth and the stock market at large. This, therefore, is a good study of how related investment data and stock performance metrics bring out in finality the connection exhibited in strategic government funding and positive stock market outcomes of companies like Jindal Steel, SAIL, Tata Steel, and Larsen & Toubro. The paper will, therefore, go on to discuss the investments of Rs 5.25 lakh crores in the railway sector during fiscal year 2024-31 showing the resultant growth of the stock prices and P/E ratios. The study also highlights the importance of key projects, such as Vande Bharat trains and Mumbai-Ahmedabad high-speed rail, in acting as growth drivers for the company's performance. Overall, the paper will provide some very vital insights into the way government investments act as a driver for development at large and in stock market performance in the Indian railway sector.

Keywords: Stocks, India, Government, Railways, Investment, Tata Steel, SAIL, L&T

1. INTRODUCTION

Government investments are crucial for generating wealth and saving money. Consequently, governments play an important role in creating an environment that encourages investments. To achieve this, the government introduces new policies and schemes for the benefit of the general public. In particular, government investments in equity include direct investments in share capital, conversion of outstanding loans against entities into equity, and conversions of dividends declared by entities into equity (OECD, 2011). Moreover, the government invests in micro, small, and medium business enterprises, tourism, startups, agriculture, and handloom and textile

industries. As a result, government investments provide many benefits. One of the main reasons for government investments is the promotion of economic growth, which is achieved by offering projects and contracts to medium and large-cap companies and financing public infrastructure projects such as constructing highways, railway lines, roads, and airports (CFI Team, 2023).

For instance, as of September 2023, the Indian Government has invested Rupees 25,813 crores in the pharmaceutical industry, leading to a major increase in the stocks of pharmaceutical companies such as Sun Pharmaceuticals, Dr. Reddy’s Laboratories, Cipla, and Lupin (PTI, 2023). Subsequently, there has been an increase in the P/E ratios of these stocks as well.

Figure 1: Government Investments in Railways (2008-2022)(Billion USD)

In terms of specific investments, the Indian Government has significantly invested in railways. Figure 1 above represents the value of government investments in railways from 2008 to 2022 in India. There is an upward trend in the value of government investments. From 2008 to 2012, the value was 31.03 billion USD. From 2013 to 2017, the government invested 58.96 billion US Dollars, while the amount rose to 124.13 billion US Dollars from 2018 to 2022 (Statista, 2021).

In addition, the Indian Government is taking new initiatives to upgrade railways in India. Some of these initiatives include the introduction and development of Vande Bharat by the Indian Government, the introduction of semi-high-speed rails, the announcement of Mission Raftaar with the target of increasing the average speed of freight and superfast mail trains, and the upgrading of tracks with high-strength rails (R-350) (IBEF, 2024). The Indian Railway plans to operationalize 4,500 Vande Bharat trains by 2047 (Urban Transport News, 2024). Consequently,

the government provides contracts and orders to private and public companies for railway development. These companies include Steel and Iron companies, Infrastructure development companies, and Digital Infrastructure and Telecommunication companies. As a result, there is a substantial increase in the company's share price and P/E ratio (TOI Business Desk, 2024).

One company benefiting from government investment is the Indian Railway Catering and Tourism Corporation (IRCTC). It was developed on 27th September 1999 (Wikipedia, 2024) for the upgrade and management of catering and hospitality services at stations, trains, and other locations. Therefore, the revenue growth for IRCTC is led by its core catering and Internet ticketing business. Since the last five years, there has been a growth of 500% in its share price (Yahoo Finance, 2024). IRCTC is in the process of expanding its e-catering services to cover more railway stations across the country so that more passengers can avail of the meal services online while in transit. Additionally, IRCTC has a debt-free status and is expected to be on a positive growth trajectory in the upcoming years (Equity Master, 2024).

Similarly, Rail Vikas Nigam Limited (RVNL) is an India-based company engaged in developing rail infrastructure. It works as the construction arm of the Ministry of Railways for project implementation and transportation infrastructure development (RVNL, 2024). Furthermore, RVNL successfully developed the Vallarpadam-Edapally railway link, the longest railway bridge in India. Another notable project is the Obularipalli-Krishnapatnam project, completed at the cost of Rs 2000 crores, which includes land costs and the doubling of track between Venkatachalam Road Junction and Krishnapatnam (RVNL, 2024). This electrified route features a 6.7 km tunnel, the longest electrified tunnel in India. Consequently, RVNL has experienced significant growth, with its share price increasing by around 1300% over the last five years (Yahoo Finance, 2024).

While government investments positively impact company growth, a gap exists in understanding their direct impact on stock markets. The Indian Government is active in making investments in small, mid, and large-cap companies. These investments often lead to a positive upward trend in a company's stock prices and P/E ratios. For instance, the Indian Government has invested Rs 16.93 lakh crores in power and renewable energy, along with Rs 17.05 lakh crores in pipeline sectors since 2014. As a result, there has been a gigantic increase in the stock prices of companies in these sectors over the last 10 years (PTI, 2024).

In contrast, the Telecom sector also plays a major role in developing the digital economy due to active government investments. As a result, there has been a positive growth in the stock prices and P/E ratios of major companies in the Telecom sector. Over the last year, the stock prices of Bharti Airtel and VI have increased by 66% and 123%, respectively (MoneyControl, 2024).

Furthermore, the railway ministry has decided to invest Rs 5.25 lakh crores during FY2024-31, resulting in a growth of more than 20% in the stock prices of companies in the railway sector. Some of these companies include Rail Vikas Nigam Ltd, Indian Railway Catering and Tourism Corporation, Indian Railway Finance Corporation Ltd, and Iacon International (Trade Brains, 2023).

In a related development, the US government invested USD 553 million in Gautam Adani's Sri Lanka ports in November 2023 to counter China's influence. This investment boosted the share price of Adani Ports by around 50% and its P/E ratio (metadata agency, 2023).

Investments are essential in driving economic growth and development, as demonstrated by their positive impact on companies and their stock performances. The paper aims to link the stock prices of various companies in the Railway sector with various government investments and government contracts.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Aim

The research utilizes a quantitative analysis of stock market data, supplemented by a descriptive analysis of government interventions and infrastructure projects. This mixed-method approach allows the study to examine the impact of government investments in the Indian Railways sector and their influence on the stock market. The research also considers the wider economic implications of these investments on related industries such as steel, construction, and infrastructure, with a specific focus on companies like Jindal Steel, SAIL, Tata Steel, and Larsen & Toubro. The study collects stock prices, market capitalization, P/E ratios, and other key performance indicators (KPIs) of publicly listed companies related to the railway sector, as well as those in steel and infrastructure that benefit from railway investments. The data has been collected for 2025-31. Details of government investments in Indian Railways, are compiled from budget documents, public sector reports, and railway ministry publications. Information on key infrastructure projects such as Vande Bharat trains, the Mumbai-Ahmedabad high-speed rail, and

the modernization of stations is gathered to highlight the specific impacts of these initiatives on stock prices.

2.2 Data Analysis

This method assesses the cumulative abnormal returns (CAR) of the selected companies' stocks around significant government announcements and project inaugurations, such as the Vande Bharat trains and the Mumbai-Ahmedabad high-speed rail. The stock price trends and P/E ratios of companies are analyzed before, during, and after the announcement of major railway investments.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section shows the impact of various government investments on the share prices and P/E ratios of companies like Jindal Steel, SAIL, Tata Steel, and Larsen & Toubro. This includes a graphical analysis and comparison of the share prices and P/E ratios of the companies over the last 5 years.

The study's results demonstrate the significant impact of government investments on stock market trends, particularly in the railway sector.

Figure 2: Jindal Steel's P/E Ratio and Share Price (2021-2024)

Figure 2 shows that Jindal Steel's P/E ratio in March 2021 was 9.65, but there was a decline in March 2022 due to the increasing number of daily COVID-19 cases and deaths (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). However, from 2022 to 2024, there has been an upward trend in the P/E ratio, with values of 13.96 (Smart-Investing.in, 2024) and 17.66 in March 2023 and June 2024, respectively (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). Currently, as of June 2024, Jindal Steel's P/E ratio

stands at 35.5. Additionally, Jindal Steel's operating profits for the last three years have been Rupees 11,168, 2,872, and 7,150 (in crores) respectively. Furthermore, Jindal Steel is the first private company in India to be granted 'Regular Rail Supplier' status by the Indian Railways, supplying a comprehensive range of approved rails and head-hardened rails, thus contributing to India's self-reliance in this domain (The New Indian Times, 2020).

Notably, Jindal Steel received multiple projects from the Indian Railways, including the rail order for the supply of 100k MT of rails to Indian Railways in 2019. Moreover, Jindal Steel's specialty rails are used in a marquee project of Indian Railways—the Udampur-Srinagar-Baramulla rail link project in Jammu and Kashmir (Jindal Stainless, 2023). Jindal Steel's value-added steel is utilized in railways and metros, achieving a cost saving of H10.26 Crores through lean chemistry implementation in structural and high-tensile grades at Rail Mill at JSP Raigarh. As a result, these projects have significantly contributed to the gigantic increase in Jindal Steel's share price and P/E ratio, leading to an increase of around 625% in its share price over the last five years (Yahoo Finance, 2024).

In addition to Jindal Steel, the analysis of the Steel Authority of India (SAIL) indicates similar trends. In March 2019, SAIL's P/E ratio was 9.44, but there was a downward trend in the financial year 2019-2020, with the P/E ratio dropping to 4.49 in 2020 (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). Nevertheless, a slight rise occurred in the financial year 2020-2021, with a P/E ratio of 7.85 in March 2021 (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). However, in March 2022, there was a tremendous fall in the P/E ratio, valued at 3.32 due to the rising number of COVID-19 cases (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). At the end of 2022, the company had a P/E ratio of 9.77. Subsequently, there was an incredible increase in the P/E ratio in March 2023 and 2024, with values of 15.75 and 23.09 as of June 6, 2024, respectively (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). Additionally, SAIL's operating profits for the last three years have been Rupees 12,015, 1,903, and 2,733 (in crores), respectively (Moneycontrol, 2024).

Importantly, SAIL has a dominant presence in the steel, mining, and infrastructure sectors, receiving multiple projects and orders from the Indian Railways. These projects include the Rishikesh-Karanprayag Rail Link, the Udampur-Srinagar-Baramulla Railway Line, the Bullet Train Project (Ahmedabad to Mumbai), and various metro rail projects (SAIL, 2023) SAIL also finalized an MoU with Western Railways in December 2022 regarding flash butt welding at the Sabarmati Workshop (SAIL, 2021). In FY 2022-23, the total loading of long rails at 9.38 Lakh

tonnes was the best, surpassing the previous best of 7.36 lakh tonnes in FY 2020-21 (SAIL, 2020). A total of 11.70 lakh tonnes of rails were supplied to Indian Railways in FY 2022-23. These projects and orders resulted in an increase of 220% in the company’s share price in the past 5 years (SAIL, 2022). There has also been a significant increase in the stock’s P/E ratio (Finbox.com, 2024).

Figure 3: SAIL's P/E Ratio and Share Price (2019-2024)

The SAIL-RITES joint venture received a wagon order of Rupees 818 crores from the Indian Railways in April 2023. This significantly contributed to a positive trend in the P/E ratio of the stock in the financial year 2024-2025 (Mishra, 2024). As seen in Figure 3, there was a significant rise in SAIL’s P/E ratio and share price. Furthermore, SAIL, along with Tata Steel and Jindal Steel, received a government tender for supplying steel worth rupees 1,586 crores to the Indian Railways. This also positively impacted the stock’s P/E ratio (Staff S, 2024).

The analysis of Tata Steel further supports these findings. Despite a downward trend in the P/E ratio of Tata Steel due to negative EPS (negative net profit), the company’s P/E ratio peaked at an all-time high of 14.56 in March 2023 (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). At the end of the financial year in 2019, SAIL’S P/E ratio was valued at 9.44. In March 2020, SAIL’s P/E ratio was valued at 4.49. At the end of 2022, the company had a P/E ratio of 8.18. As of June 2024, the P/E ratio is valued at -44.26 (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). Additionally, Tata Steel's operating profits for the last three years have been Rupees 33,011, 15,495, and 4,807 (in crores), respectively (Smart-Investing.in, 2024).

Figure 4: Tata Steel's P/E Ratio and Share Price (2019-2024)

Tata Steel introduced the New Materials Business in 2018, playing a major role in providing sustainable lightweight solutions to the railway sector (Tata Steel, 2023). Moreover, Tata Steel announced itself as an integrated solutions provider to Indian Railways by delivering a fully furnished first AC coach to Modern Coach Factory, Raebareli (Tata Steel, 2023). Tata Steel was awarded an order for a complete seating system for 23 train sets and complete interior furnishing solutions for 16 trainsets of the Vande Bharat Express by the Indian Railways (Tata Steel, 2023). Additionally, Tata Steel received orders for reusable steel pallets for packaging, replacing traditional wooden pallets in 2021-22 (Tata Steel, 2022). As indicated in Figure 4, there was a significant increase in the company's P/E ratio and share price in March 2022. Tata Steel's outbound logistics is 60% dependent on Indian Railways. Therefore, Tata Steel's Railway Segment focuses on providing the best-in-class railway interiors to Indian passengers (Tata Steel, 2017). Consequently, these projects have significantly contributed to the increase in Tata Steel's share price and P/E ratio, resulting in a 270% increase in the company's share price over the last five years (Smart-Investing, 2024).

Tata Steel received an order to manufacture 22 Vande Bharat trains in 2023. Despite the falling P/E ratio of the stock, the stock price increased in the financial year of 2023-2024 due to multiple projects from the Indian Railways (Smart-Investing, 2024). Furthermore, Tata Steel, in partnership with South Eastern Railway, received a tender from the Indian Railways for the development of the Green Rail Project in February 2024, leading to a share price increase from Rupees 144 to 174 (Smart-Investing, 2024).

Lastly, the analysis of Larsen and Toubro (L&T) highlights a positive trend in the P/E ratio. The P/E ratio of L&T in March 2019 was 21.8, but it declined to 11.86 in March 2020 (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). Since March 2020, there has been a positive trend in the P/E ratio of

L&T. There was a major surge in the P/E ratio of the stock in the financial year of 2021-2022 (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). The P/E ratios in 2021, 2022, 2023, and 2024 were 17.2, 28.65, 29.06, and 30.78, respectively (Smart-Investing.in, 2024). L&T's operating profits for the last three years have been Rupees 7,879, 7,848, and 9,304 (in crores), respectively (MoneyControl, 2024).

Figure 5: L&T's P/E Ratio and Share Price (2019-2024)

Larsen and Toubro is well known for its construction and infrastructural development projects. Construction and maintenance of railways and rail bridges contribute to 20% of its total turnover (Larsen and Toubro, 2023). The company has completed many projects, including the Metro Link Express for Gandhinagar and Ahmedabad (MEGA) Track Package in Gujarat (66 TKM) in 2022 (Larsen and Toubro, 2023). The Hyderabad Metro Rail project, executed through a wholly owned subsidiary, L&T Metro Rail Hyderabad Limited, is the world's largest PPP Project in the metro sector (Larsen and Toubro, 2022). QR ticketing (Digital & Paper) introduced by L&T MRHL is already making travel contactless, easy, and hassle-free for commuters (Larsen and Toubro, 2023). L&T MRHL has become India's first metro rail to roll out a WhatsApp-based e-ticketing System (Larsen and Toubro, 2022). L&T played a significant role in designing, developing, manufacturing, and supplying Track-Slab Laying Cars and Rail Feeder Cars for India's High-Speed Rail project (Larsen and Toubro, 2022). It received the Mumbai-Ahmedabad high-speed rail project, which also won the Apex India Green Leaf award in 2021 in the 'gold category' for achieving environmental excellence (Larsen and Toubro, 2023).

As a result, L&T's share price and P/E ratio have seen a gigantic increase due to these infrastructural projects from the Indian Railways. L&T's share price has increased by 130% in the last five years (Larsen and Toubro, 2023).

Larsen and Toubro received a mega contract of Rupees 12,500 crores to construct a part of the Mumbai-Ahmedabad bullet train project from a Japanese agency in January 2024 (Shukla, 2024). This is a major reason for the hike in the share price of L&T and a slight increase in its P/E ratio (Smart-Investing, 2024). As indicated in Figure 5, there was a substantial increase in the company's share price in January 2024. Furthermore, Larsen and Toubro accepted a contract of Rupees 1040.51 crores from Rail Infrastructure Development Company, Karnataka, for constructing an elevated viaduct for Bengaluru Suburban rail in January 2024 (Shah, 2023). This significantly led to an increase in its share price and a slight increase in its P/E ratio (Smart-Investing, 2024).

In conclusion, the results and discussion sections highlight the positive impact of government investments on stock market trends and company growth, particularly in the railway sector. These investments have driven significant increases in share prices and P/E ratios for companies such as Jindal Steel, SAIL, Tata Steel, and Larsen and Toubro. Overall, government investments have played a crucial role in shaping the economic landscape and fostering growth across various industries.

4. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the government's investment has a significant effect on stock market trends in India, more so in the railway sector. The positive relationship between government funding and stock market performance can be explained by the rapid growth of companies like Jindal Steel, SAIL, Tata Steel, and Larsen & Toubro in India. It can be analyzed from the data that strategic investments, like the ones in the railway sector, increase stock prices and P/E ratios. Added to this are some government-backed projects, like Vande Bharat trains and Mumbai-Ahmedabad high-speed rail, which have contributed to the economic betterment of these companies. The findings thus underline the fact that government investments are among the driving forces of economic growth and play a critical role in the shaping of stock market dynamics. However, this study has certain limitations as well. The stock market is affected by multiple factors like inflation, political factors, economic trends, and investor sentiments. This study may not have accounted for all external factors that could have impacted the results. The findings of this study are limited to the effect of government investments on some Indian companies and are specific to India and its unique political, economic, and regulatory landscape.

The results may not apply to other countries. This research provides an understanding of how government investments can bolster company performance and stimulate broader economic development in India. While the railway sector has been the key focus in this study, future studies can explore other sectors like the energy sector, pharmaceuticals sector, infrastructure sector, and technology sector. Further research could explore the comparative impacts of government investment versus private sector investment on stock market performance.

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